

Alkali Metal Complexes : Complexes of Alkali Metal Glycinates with Some Oxygen and Nitrogen Donor Ligands

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Compounds of the general formula $M. Gly. nHL$ (where $M = Li, Na, K, Rb$ and Cs ; $Gly =$ glycinate, $n = 1, 2$ or 3 and $HL = 8$ -hydroxyquinoline, 1-nitroso-2-naphthol, isonitrosoacetophenone, *o*-nitrophenol and acetylacetonone), have been synthesised by reaction between alkali metal glycinates and HL in absolute ethanol. With the values of $n = 2$ and 3 , together with high transition temperatures of several 1:3 complexes of Rb and Cs suggest a coordination number 6 or greater than six. The attachment of the second ligands (with lower pK values than glycine) to the metal glycinates also points out that pK is not the only dominant factor in the formation of these mixed ligand complexes.

IN recent years the formation of complexes containing two different ligands has become of interest to coordination chemists. Since all of these studies have involved transition and rare-earth metals, we thought that it would be of interest to study the same phenomena with the alkali-metals. Moreover, in view of the suggestion that rare-earths and alkaline earth ions exhibit a maximum coordination number larger than six, which is commonly assumed, we thought that it might be possible to obtain more evidence in support of this idea, that coordination number of a metal ion may be greater than six, by investigating some selected mixed ligand complexes of alkali metals.

For this study the ligands which form very stable 1 : 1 alkali-metal chelates (glycinate, β -alaninate) are chosen, and the tendency of these chelates to bind a second ligand are looked into. Essentially the system then corresponds to measuring the formation of $ML.HL'$ from ML and HL' . The chosen 1 : 1 salts are neutral (and chelate), thus minimising the electrostatic repulsion towards the incoming ligand HL' .

We chose the amino acids because of its presence in many biological systems and because it provides a potential binding site for the metal ions. As such a thorough knowledge of the coordinating property of the amino acids (with possible change of the coordinating groups, a change from closed chain to open chain compounds) is, therefore, necessary to understand more fully the role of alkali-metal ions in such systems.

The syntheses and characterisation of complexes of alkali-metal salts of glycine with 8-hydroxyquinoline, 1-nitroso-2-naphthol, isonitrosoacetophenone, *o*-nitrophenol and acetylacetonone are described in the present communication.

Experimental

To a saturated ethanol solution of the glycinates, the second ligands (in solid) were added (mole ratio 1 : 4). The mixture was refluxed in a water bath for 15 min. when everything went into solution. On cooling (in some cases after overnight cooling in a refrigerator) the corresponding mixed ligand complexes separated out, which were filtered, washed with cold absolute ethanol, and dried in an oven at 80° . Special care was taken not to add too much of the second ligand, as otherwise, the ligand separated out on cooling along with the mixed ligand complexes.

Results and Discussions

All the compounds are stable in dry air but decompose rapidly on exposure to moisture. These solid adducts have higher melting points than the stoichiometric mixture of their components; the transition or decomposition temperature of the complexes are much higher than that of the ligands, showing their greater stability. The colour, decomposition or transition temperatures and analytical values of these complexes are given in Table 1.

The second ligands which have lower pK values than glycine, also formed adducts with glycine salts and do not replace the glycine from the metal salts. This suggests that pK is not the only dominant factor in the formation of these alkali-metal adducts. One of the factors may be the chelating ability of the ligand towards the metal ion, as has been experienced in case of mixed ligand complexes of transition metal complexes.

TABLE 1

Compound	Colour	Transition (t°C) or decomp.(d°C)	Found			Calculated		
			C	H	M	C	H	M
LiGly.8HQ	White	160 t	57.98	5.02		58.40	4.86	
NaGly.8HQ	White	140 t	55.10	4.63	9.46	54.55	4.54	9.50
K Gly.(8HQ) ₂	White	135 t	56.80	4.84	7.77	57.44	4.61	8.11
RbGly.(8HQ) ₂	White	125 t	52.92	4.60	10.85	53.36	4.44	11.45
CsGly.(8HQ) ₂	White	116 t	49.78	4.36	15.89	50.19	4.16	16.73
LiGly.1N2N	Light brown	180 t	55.80	4.48		56.69	4.33	
NaGly.1N2N	Brown	165 t	52.68	4.22	7.95	53.33	4.07	8.51
K Gly.(1N2N) ₂	Brown	140 t	53.98	4.07	7.45	54.03	4.12	7.31
RbGly.(1N2N) ₂	Brown	130 t	49.16	3.84	10.96	49.74	3.79	11.22
CsGly.(1N2N) ₂	Brown	125 t	46.23	3.64	21.25	46.00	3.51	21.10
LiGly.INAP	Pale yellow	135 t	51.87	5.03		52.17	4.78	
NaGly.INAP	Pale yellow	125 t	48.12	5.16	8.84	48.77	4.74	9.34
K Gly.(INAP) ₂	Pale yellow	115 t	51.80	4.68	8.98	52.55	4.37	9.48
RbGly.(INAP) ₂	Pale yellow	112 t	46.65	4.55	17.70	47.04	3.93	18.59
CsGly.(INAP) ₂	Pale yellow	108 t	41.93	3.65	25.88	42.85	3.57	26.19
LiGly.acac	White	240 d	45.86	7.12		46.40	6.62	
NaGly.acac	White	170 d	42.20	6.20	11.25	42.62	6.09	11.67
K Gly.(acac) ₂	White	194 d	41.23	5.50	11.73	41.73	5.79	11.30
RbGly.(acac) ₂	White	200 d	38.84	5.49	15.60	39.00	5.36	16.25
CsGly.(acac) ₂	White	210 d	34.80	5.00	21.80	35.78	4.91	22.98
LiGly.ONP	Yellow	230 d	42.85	4.20		43.63	4.09	
NaGly.ONP	Yellow	220 d	39.88	4.05	9.98	40.67	3.81	9.74
K Gly.(ONP) ₂	Yellow	125 d	43.12	6.63	10.10	43.07	3.58	10.00
RbGly.(ONP) ₂	Yellow	200 d	43.12	3.07	14.85	41.66	3.29	14.75
CsGly.(ONP) ₂	Yellow	180 d	38.40	3.08	20.98	38.52	3.02	21.18

Gly = Glycine ; 8HQ = 8-Hydroxyquinoline ; 1N2N = 1-Nitroso-2-naphthol ; INAP = isonitrosoacetophenone ; acac = acetylacetone ; and ONP = *o*-Nitrophenol.

TABLE 2—SELECTED ABSORPTION BANDS IN DIFFERENT REGIONS (CM⁻¹)

Compound	3500—3300	2800—2300	2300—1800	1700—1500
8-Hydroxyquinoline (8HQ)				
LiGly.8HQ	3400		2100 br	1580 (C=N)
NaGly.8HQ	3180		1660sh	1610 1580
K Gly.(8HQ) ₂	3200 3100	2600	2150 br	1660sh 1610 1575 1540 1500
RbGly.(8HQ) ₂	3100	2580 br	2160 br	1665sh 1610 1570 1540 1500
CsGly.(8HQ) ₂	3400—3100br	2580 br	2150 br	1665sh 1610 1580 1560 1530 1500
2160			1665—1610br	1580 1560 1530 1500
1-Nitroso-2-naphthol (1N2N)				
LiGly.1N2N	3300br 3055			1640 (N=O)
NaGly.1N2N	3160	2700 br, 2590br	2100	1640 1595 1540 1500
K Gly.(1N2N) ₂	3410br	2600 br		1620 1595 1560 1505
RbGly.(1N2N) ₂	3400br	2600 br	1630sh	1615 1590 1560 1505
CsGly.(1N2N) ₂	3400br	2600 br	1640sh	1620 1580 1550 1500
2400 br			1660 1640	1610 1560 1500
Isonitrosoacetophenone (INAP)				
LiGly.INAP	3260			1680 (C=O)
NaGly.INAP	3165s	2710 2600 2510	2110	1650 1590 1520 1500
K Gly.(INAP) ₂	3165s	2710 2600 2510	2110	1650 1590 1550 1510
RbGly.(INAP) ₂	3160br	2700	2140	1660 1620sh 1590 1550 1510
CsGly.(INAP) ₂	3170s	2740 2600 2510	2120	1660 1620sh 1590 1550 1520 1500
3160 3100		2680 2600	2240 2160	1660 1620 1590 1550 1500
<i>o</i>-Nitrophenol (ONP)				
LiGly.ONP	3218			1615 (N=O)
NaGly.ONP	3400br 3180	2740 2610	2130	1660 1610 1520 1505
K Gly.(ONP) ₂	3410br 3100	2600	2130	1660 1620 1590 1520 1500
RbGly.(ONP) ₂	3410br 3100	2700 2600	2130	1660 1620 1590 1530 1503
CsGly.(ONP) ₂	3430br 3160br		2140 br	1660sh 1620—1590br 1500 1500
3430br 3100		2710 2600	2200	1660sh 1620—1580br 1530 1500
Acetylacetone (acac)				
LiGly.acac	3420br 3110	2620	2180	1735 1720 1625br 1660sh 1635 1610 1550 1500
NaGly.acac	3430br 3100	2600	2200	1660sh 1635—1610br 1550sh 1500
K Gly.(acac) ₂	3420br 3100	2600	2160	1660sh 1635—1580br 1550sh 1500
RbGly.(acac) ₂	3400br			1660sh 1610—1500br 1500
CsGly.(acac) ₂	3420br 3100	2600	2160	1660sh 1630 1600 1560sh 1500

In our previous work we observed that in the mixed ligand complexes of the general formula ML_nHL' , n had always been one. With glycinate adducts, the value of n is one only for lithium and sodium, whereas in potassium, rubidium and caesium adducts, the number of second ligand is more than one. An increase in the number of second ligand in the adducts appeared to be favoured, by increase in the radius or possibly decrease in the ionisation potential, of the alkali-metal.

Infrared spectra

The spectra of the mixed ligand complexes of metal glycinate and other O-, and N-donor ligands (Table 2), show a number of unexpected features.

Firstly, the O-H stretching frequency of the second ligand is either absent or shifted down by 100-150 cm^{-1} with reduced intensity.

Secondly, the $-\text{NH}_2$ stretching region (3450 - 3200 cm^{-1}) show the very broad, poorly resolved absorptions, typical of strongly hydrogen bonded $-\text{NH}_2$ groups. In most of the cases, this absorption band is absent.

Thirdly, a new broad band of medium intensity with sub-maxima between 2710 and 2550 cm^{-1} is seen in all the complexes, which is absent in the metal salt or the second ligand.

Fourthly, another new band of weak to medium intensity (in few cases strong, especially in Rb- and Cs-complexes) is exhibited by most of the complexes around 2200 cm^{-1} . In few cases this band is exhibited at about 1800 cm^{-1} .

The disappearance of the O-H band of the second ligand (or with its shift of 150 cm^{-1}) and reappearance between 2700-1800 cm^{-1} , suggests that there is strong hydrogen bonding. The precise manner in which the proton is hydrogen bonded can not be stated, but the following possibilities exist: (1) to the oxygen/nitrogen of the same ligand, (2) to the oxygen/nitrogen of one of the bidentate ligands bound to the same metal ion, (3) to the oxygen/nitrogen of a ligand bound to a neighbouring metal ion.

When the hydrogen bonding is weak the bands appear above 2600 cm^{-1} and for strong hydrogen bonding, bands occur between 2200 and 1800 cm^{-1} . Utilising the relationship given by Lord and Merryfield⁸, the hydrogen bonded oxygen-oxygen distance in these complexes have been estimated to lie between 2.5 - 2.6 Å. These values, however, have only a comparative significance as many other factors influence the oxygen-oxygen distance.

In most of the mixed ligand complexes of alkali-metal glycinate, the absorption bands characteristic¹⁻⁴ of the hydrogen bonded $>\text{NH}$ are present in the infrared spectra. On the other hand in most, the diagnostic $>\text{NH}^+$ bands are absent.

The broad 2500 cm^{-1} band is a composite band and its displacement from the normal $>\text{NH}^+$ stretching frequency ($\sim 3200 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) has been attributed to strong hydrogen bonding of the type $^+\text{N} \cdots \text{H} \cdots \text{O} \cdots \text{L}$. The extreme band width is probably due to intermolecular interactions.

Norman⁵ in his oxime complexes reports a diffuse absorption area in the region 3100-1700 cm^{-1} , with broad peaks at approximately 2500 and 1850 cm^{-1} . Such a phenomenon had been noted in the spectra of amino acids and is attributed to Zwitterion formation^{6,7}. Bellamy⁸ ascribed these peaks to $\text{N}^+ - \text{H}$ groupings. Similar broad peaks have been noted^{9,10} in the spectra of isonicotinic, quinaldonic and cinchoninic acids and have been ascribed to very strong hydrogen bonding between carbonyl oxygen and the ring hetero nitrogen atom.

None of these mixed ligand complexes show anomalous and broad absorption bands between 700-1300 cm^{-1} , as such acid salt structure with very short $\text{O} \cdots \text{H} \cdots \text{O}$ (ca 2.4 Å) is most improbable.

All the second ligands are potential chelates and provide two binding sites for metal ions. One of these is the hydroxyl group (O-H) and the infrared spectra of the complexes suggest a strong hydrogen bonding in most of the cases. The bands corresponding to the second site of attachment in these ligands, C=N for 8HQ, N=O for 1N2N, C=O for INAP, N=O for ONP and C=O for acac., have been found to be metal sensitive.

Adducts with 8-hydroxyquinoline give spectra closely similar to that of the silver complex. There are minor but diagnostic differences between the Li and Na, MGly (8HQ) and K, Rb and Cs, MGly (8HQ)₂ or 3. It is possible that the smaller cations are tetrahedrally coordinated like the silver, while the larger ones are octahedrally coordinated. The third molecule of 8HQ in Rb- and Cs- complexes may be loosely attached. Coordination is suggested by the i. r. band found at 1580 cm^{-1} (C=N) in the ligand and the Li-complex and at lower frequencies with increase in atomic weight of M until for Cs it appears at 1560 cm^{-1} . In Rb- and Cs- complexes, there appears an extra band at 1580 cm^{-1} , which may be due to the third 8HQ molecule attached loosely.

In 1-nitroso-2-naphthol complexes, Li is different from the rest in having a medium band at 3160 cm^{-1} , which is missing in the rest. The Na, K and Rb complexes show weak and broad bands centred around 3400 cm^{-1} but no band between 2200-1800 cm^{-1} ; whereas Cs shows a strong band at 1920 cm^{-1} with no bands above 3000 cm^{-1} . The N=O band at 1400 cm^{-1} again is metal sensitive and shows downward trend with increase in atomic weight (except Rb). Cs-complex shows an extra band at 1640 cm^{-1} .

Mixed ligand complexes of isonitrosoacetophenone show a strong band centred around 3160 cm^{-1} for all the metals from Li to Cs, whereas the ligand OH stretch

is 3260 cm^{-1} . Again the Li and Na spectra of MGly (INAP) is different from that of K, Rb and Cs spectra of MGly (INAP)₂ which may be due to tetrahedral and octahedral structure of the respective complexes. The C=O ligand band at 1680 cm^{-1} is metal sensitive and shows variation from 1650 cm^{-1} to 1620 cm^{-1} with increase in atomic weight of the metal. The K, Rb and Cs complexes show an extra band at 1660 cm^{-1} , which may be due to extra ligand and octahedral structure.

The *o*-nitrophenol adducts show two broad medium bands above 3000 cm^{-1} ; one centred around 3400 cm^{-1} and the other at 3100 cm^{-1} . Over and above these $>\text{NH}-\text{O}$ bands at 2700 cm^{-1} and $\text{O}-\text{H}\cdots\text{O}$ bands at 2100 cm^{-1} are also present. The additional molecules may have intramolecular hydrogen bands rather than intermolecular ones, as suggested by the observation that no adducts are formed with *m*-nitrophenol. Further it has been observed that N=O ligand band at 1615 cm^{-1} is not metal sensitive. So these compounds are unlikely to be complexes, although each anion may chelate two or three cations, as in the hemihydrate of $\text{K.ONP} \cdot \frac{1}{2}\text{H}_2\text{O}^{11}$.

Assignments in the carbonyl region $1500-1700\text{ cm}^{-1}$ for acac complexes are somewhat uncertain. Hancock et al. studied about fifty acetylacetonate complexes with metal ions and found that for ionic complexes $\nu(\text{C}=\text{C}) > \nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ and that $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O}) > \nu(\text{C}=\text{C})$ for covalent complexes.^{12,13} On the basis of evidence put forward by Nakamoto¹⁴ the highest frequency band at 1605 cm^{-1} in acetylacetonate is assigned to a C=C stretching vibration, and not, as was previously thought, a C=O vibration. No band attributable to the free C=O group is observed in acetylacetonate, which must therefore be completely in the mono-enolic form. The broad band centred around 1570 cm^{-1} has been assigned to a

C=O group that has had its double bond character removed by a resonance effect known as "conjugation chelation".¹⁵

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